

Precursors of Sustainable Development in William Wordsworth's Poem *The World is Too Much With Us*

Dr. Ali Hafudh Humaish

Wasit University, College of Education, English Department

Iraq

Abstract

This paper examines William Wordsworth's poem "The World is Too Much With Us" through the lens of sustainable development. Though the concept of sustainable development was first popularized in 1972 UN conference, but but the visionary power of romantic poetry predicted the concept well before this date. Written in 1807, the poem critiques the rapid industrialization and material nature of the Romantic period where it raises issues that related to contemporary concerns about environmental degradation and social sustainability. Through the poem's reflections on nature, human disassociation and the pursuit of material gain, this paper explores how Wordsworth's themes not only align with modern interpretations of sustainable development in relation to environmental conservation, social equity, and the importance of maintaining a harmonious relationship with nature but it is also an early warning from a visionary poet more than two hundred years earlier.

Keywords: sustainable, nature, environmental preservation, symbiotic, Wordsworth

The Brundtland Report (1987) defined sustainable development as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.” (Brutland, 1987). This concept encompasses environmental, economic, and social dimensions, all of which are relevant to the themes expressed in Wordsworth’s poem. Environmental sustainability involves maintaining the health of ecosystems and biodiversity, and using resources in a way that does not deplete them for future generations. Wordsworth’s concern for the exploitation of nature aligns with this principle, as his poem critiques the disregard for nature in favor of material wealth.

Wordsworth’s critique in the poem “ The World is tooMuch with us” is often regarded as a response to the commodification of nature—a process accelerated by industrial growth and urban expansion. Guerria affirms that :

Biodiversity is declining at an unprecedented rate, threatening the achievement of the SDGs, especially for the more than two billion people who depend directly on nature for their livelihoods. COVID-19 has further highlighted the importance of the relationship between people, nature, and, prosperity, and shows us how important it is to leave no one behind. This set of sessions takes a closer look at how protecting, restoring and sustainably managing nature can help us achieve the SDGs, especially those related to climate, health, security, water, and prosperity.(Gurria, 2020)

There is no doubt that most romantic poets had visions about the world that later came true. William Blake’s vision, for example, about childhood, human nature, love and social injustice where the precursors to much of our contemporary life. William Wordsworth’s obsession with nature is yet another example of a poet was able to predict the importance of the maintaining of a healthy environment to sustain our existence.

The poem is a sonnet that critiques humanity’s increasing detachment from nature. Wordsworth expresses lament for the growing materialism and industrialization of the modern world, suggesting that this shift leads to a loss of spiritual and natural connection. This research explores how Wordsworth’s poem reflects early concerns about the principles of sustainable

development, particularly regarding environmental preservation, the ethical consequences of industrialization, and the importance of a symbiotic relationship between humanity and nature

The poet starts his poem with a sad tone that we have been indulged in a spree of spending and wasting nature's resources without much attention to our environment:

The world is too much with us; late and soon,

Getting and spending, we lay waste our powers;—

Little we see in Nature that is ours;

Gutman says that

According to Wordsworth, we have fallen in love with the wrong thing, “given our hearts away,” and paradoxically, powerfully, the excess of “too much” is now clearly a loss, the loss of our hearts. So we march through our lives without a heart, caught up in getting and spending, trapped in a mercantile world, cut off from ourselves (we no longer are in touch with Nature and the natural self). This is – a most ironic phrase – the modern “boon” (from the Old Norse, “blessing”), to be cut off from nature and without a heart, to be in thrall to something that does not sustain us. No wonder the “boon” is “sordid” – dirty, wretched, squalid. (Gutman, 2025)

The last line is a poignant deploration of our ignorance of the importance of discerning the relationship between our life and the potential of sustainability. We are completely blind to the importance of preserving nature. “ According to Wordsworth, we did not see anything in nature that is ours, though the continuation of future generations entirely depends on our sustaining and protective mode of living. it's a call for maintaining a healthy and sustainable way of spending. The word “ Wasting” is a clear indication of a non sustainable and consumerist way of living.Industrialization was beginning to shape society when Wordsworth wrote the poem. Factories, urbanization, and technological advancement brought about significant changes, many

of which Wordsworth viewed as detrimental to human connection with nature. Corfman comments that “ They are tied up in their greed for more money and their time is accounted for by their actions of getting money, spending money, and caring for their possessions. He believes that money and worldly possessions are far more important to people than they should be” (Crofman, 2025) Then he continues :

The winds that will be howling at all hours,

And are up-gathered now like sleeping flowers;

The flowers “sleep”. Giving these parts of nature human attributes helps the reader to feel this connection with nature. It paints a picture of nature and allows the reader to understand what he is missing out on by being caught up in worldly possessions and greed. The flowers “sleep”. Giving these parts of nature human attributes helps the reader to feel this connection with nature. It paints a picture of nature and allows the reader to understand what he is missing out on by being caught up in worldly possessions and greed.

The poet then proceed to discuss a deeper connection with nature to show what we miss. He uses the phenomenon of the ebb and tide and the influence of the moon on the movement of the sea. Rising and ebbing tides happen as Earth's landmasses rotate through the tidal bulges created by the Moon's gravitational pull. So here Wordsworth highlights how nature affects us in every possible way. The image makes us see this relationship:

We have given our hearts away, a sordid boon!

This Sea that bares her bosom to the moon;

The lines show that we have lost our connection with nature without realizing the consequences that might ensue. The words “ sordid boon” summarizes how we are obsessed with what nature can give us totally ignoring that this boon can become sordid if we do not follow a sustainable way of harvesting nature. Poet stresses the importance of a spiritual and emotional association with nature, suggesting that without this bond, humanity loses a critical source of moral and ethical guidance. Wordsworth contrasts the shallow, materialistic pursuit of wealth with the

deep, restorative power of nature, advocating for a balanced relationship between humans and their environment. Wordsworth says that :

For this, for everything, we are out of tune;

It moves us not.

We are “ out of tune” with nature. We use the resources with heeding consequences of destroying nature. He expresses sorrow that people no longer understand or appreciate nature’s power, focusing instead on the pursuit of “getting and spending.” This critique can be seen as an early form of environmental advocacy, suggesting that modern humans’ over-consumption and exploitation of resources are harmful to both the environment and society. The poet wishes he were a pagan rather than a Christian, who would regarding nature sacred. The Romans and Greeks idealized nature and created gods for every single phenomenon in appreciation of the importance of their environment. Something that modern man has totally ignored:

Great God! I’d rather be

A Pagan suckled in a creed outworn;

So might I, standing on this pleasant lea,

Creed or a belief that allows him To stand watching and enjoying the beautiful and pleasant scene of the beautiful meadows is for him more valued than agreed or a belief that ignores and destroys the environment. The poem aims to show how modernity has diminished the individual’s sense of identity. It further hints that life in contemporary cities has contributed towards the uniformity of experience people face, therefore making it impossible for them to escape their society’s attempts at conformity.

The first eight lines of the poem use the word “we” as a collective pronoun, thereby stressing the idea that with progress, the individual gets lost within the crowd. In industrial society, “we lay waste our powers.” A power, skill, or ability are all components that can set someone apart, but with an overarching focus on materialism that characterizes industrial society, those markers

vanish. In the end, everyone faces the same outcome: “Little we see in Nature that is ours.” The natural world functioned as a mirror, offering humans self-reflection, a tranquil counterbalance to the chaotic city. But the speaker argues that as people separate from nature, they lose that space for self-reflection. (McKusick, 2000). The preferred world of paganism that values nature for the poet is a cry to draw attention to nature. For him a glimpse of nature at the time of the pagan world is worth much more in the modern world, it makes him feel even less “forlorn”

Have glimpses that would make me less forlorn;

Have sight of Proteus rising from the sea;

Or hear old Triton blow his wreathèd horn

He would have “glimpses” of nature that would give him joy and hope, or at least make him feel “less forlorn”. He would rather be poor and helpless and connected with nature than rich and powerful and alienated from it.

In the final two lines, he refers to two pagan gods. Proteus was thought to be able to tell the future, though he avoided doing so if he could.

The speaker implies that had he been a pagan, perhaps he could imagine being in touch with Proteus, or at least catching a glimpse of him as he stares out across the sea. Triton was the pagan god that was said to be able to calm the waves of the sea. This implies that the speaker looks out at the sea, enjoying nature, long enough to see Triton and Proteus. The speaker refers to these two pagan gods after he first appeals to God and swears that he would rather be a pagan than be alienated from nature

Conclusion

Wordsworth’s “The World is Too Much With Us” provides a poignant critique of the consequences of industrialization, focusing on the loss of a spiritual connection to nature. The themes expressed in the poem align with the core principles of sustainable development, which

emphasize the importance of environmental conservation, social equity, and maintaining a balance between human progress and the natural world.

Wordsworth's concerns about industrialization and environmental degradation remain relevant today as we continue to grapple with issues such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and the social inequities exacerbated by economic growth. His poem serves as an early expression of environmental thought, one that still holds valuable lessons for modern discussions on sustainability. As the world faces unprecedented environmental crises, the themes articulated in *The World is Too Much with Us* remain highly relevant. Wordsworth's critique of materialism, his call for a deeper connection with the environment, and his vision of a more sustainable future all contribute to a timeless message that speaks directly to the current debates surrounding sustainability, environmental preservation, and the future of humanity.

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